

Linked Micromap Plots for Point Locations

Jürgen Symanzik *

Martin Holdrege †

Abstract

Only a few stand-alone attempts have been made in the past to create linked micromap plots for point locations such as climate stations and cities, rather than for areal locations (i.e., polygons). This requires that the point location is extended to a small (circular or quadratic) area that can be color-coded in a linked micromap plot. In this article, we provide an overview of necessary steps to produce linked micromap plots for point locations to create areas of suitable sizes and to avoid overplotting of nearby point locations. Three case studies will highlight the benefits of linked micromap plots for point locations.

Key Words: Maps; Visualization; Spatial Data; Software

1. Introduction

Linked micromap plots, often abbreviated as LMPlots or just called micromaps, were first presented at the 1996 American Statistical Association's (ASA) annual meeting in Chicago, Illinois (Olsen et al., 1996). They link row-labeled univariate (or multivariate) statistical summaries to a corresponding geographical region. The primary focus of LMPlots is on the statistical displays and not on the maps. LMPlots were developed to display data in its spatial context while conveying more information than a traditional choropleth map, which typically allows the reader to see only approximate values of a single variable across space.

To illustrate how LMPlots have been used in the past, we begin with an example. Figure 1 shows a LMPlot that could be seen on the experimental linked micromap web page of the Utah Climate Center (UCC) at Utah State University (USU) on May 24, 2004. An archived version of this web page from June 26, 2010, can be accessed at <https://web.archive.org/web/20100626045808/http://webcat.gis.usu.edu:8080/index.html>. The LMPlot in Figure 1 is related to the spread of the West Nile Virus (WNV) across the United States (US) in the year 2002. The leftmost column shows the colors used for the statistical areas of interest, here the 50 US states and the District of Columbia. The colors are repeated in each perceptual block of five states. Next to the colors are the state names, sorted in decreasing order of the 2002 WNV infection rates for each state. Nebraska, ranked 51, had the highest rate; Louisiana, ranked 50, had the second highest rate; and so on. The next two columns are the statistical columns in this LMPlot. The left one shows the 2002 WNV infection cases per 100,000 inhabitants for each state, displayed as a dot plot. The right one shows the total number of WNV infections in 2002 for each state, also displayed as a dot plot. On the left side of each statistical panel is the rank, where "1" represents the lowest, i.e., best, rank. Finally, in the rightmost column, a series of small maps, i.e., the micromaps are shown. Here, each micromap highlights five states at a time that relate to the names and thus to the sorting order that has been used. The micromap on top highlights Nebraska, Louisiana, Illinois, Mississippi, and Michigan that had the five highest 2002 WNV infection rates. The exact numerical values for 2002 WNV infection cases per 100,000 inhabitants and the total number of WNV infections in 2002

*Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Utah State University, Logan, UT 84322-3900, USA. E-mail: juergen.symanzik@usu.edu

†Center for Adaptable Western Landscapes, Northern Arizona University, Flagstaff, AZ 86011, USA. E-mail: martinholdrege@gmail.com

Figure 1: Screenshot from the experimental linked micromap web page at Utah State University, taken on May 24, 2004.

are shown in the same colors in the two statistical columns. Similarly, the next perceptual block of states, starting with the District of Columbia and ending with Missouri shows the same information for the states ranked 46 to 42. The corresponding micromap on the right highlights these five states in their colors, but also highlights the five states that have been shown in the micromap above in a faint yellow color. Similarly, the third micromap (from the top) highlights the states ranked 41 to 37 in their colors, but also the ten states that have been shown in the two micromaps above in a faint yellow color; and so on. Thus, from the fourth micromap (from the top), it becomes obvious that there is a strong spatial cluster of the states with the highest 2002 WNV infection rates that covers the central United States, ranging from North Dakota and Minnesota in the north and extending to Texas, Louisiana, and Mississippi in the south. A viewer of this web page could eventually scroll down and see the remaining six micromaps and the related statistical information for the other 30 (+1) states that are not shown here. A related static LMPlot that shows the data for all 50 (+1) states can be found in Symanzik et al. (2003), Figure 4. The UCC–USU micromap web page was based on the Java code that was originally provided to researchers at USU from researcher at the National Cancer Institute (NCI). Naturally, it initially closely resembled the NCI version that was accessible at the NCI State Cancer Profiles web site. Screenshots from this web site are shown in Wang et al. (2002), Figure 1, and Chen et al. (2006), Figures 1 & 2. Necessary steps to update the Java code from the NCI for use in West Nile Virus data and climate applications at USU took place around 2004 and 2005 and are documented in Chapala (2005).

Overall, LMPlots have been proven to be useful for environmental, agricultural, medical, public health, and economics data in a spatial context. Linked micromap plots and their use in the application areas mentioned above have been extensively documented in the literature, e.g., in Carr and Pierson (1996), Carr et al. (1998a), Carr et al. (1998b), Symanzik and Carr (2008), Carr and Pickle (2010), Symanzik and Carr (2013), Symanzik et al. (2014), Symanzik et al. (2016), and Symanzik et al. (2017) to mention only a few. However, when reviewing all of the examples in these past publications, it becomes obvious

that the vast majority of LMPlots are related to areal data (also called lattice data) such as countries in a geographic region of the world, US states, or counties within a state. Hardly any examples could be found in the past where the underlying statistical information that is shown in a LMPlot is related to point locations, such as climate stations, positions on the baseball field, or cities in a certain geographic region.

The focus of this article is on linked micromap plots for point locations. In Section 2, we review past applications of linked micromap plots for point locations. In Section 3, we outline general construction steps for linked micromap plots for point locations and demonstrate these steps via three case studies. We conclude this article with a discussion and outlook on current and future work in Section 4.

2. Linked Micromap Plots for Point Locations

Linked micromap plots were originally developed to overcome three key problems of choropleth maps as discussed in Symanzik and Carr (2008), namely:

- (i) Some map regions in a choropleth map can be too small to effectively show color. — In LMPlots, small regions typically get enlarged and possibly shifted to a location outside the main map area where they can be enlarged. This routinely is being done for LMPlots for the 50 (+1) US states where the District of Columbia is being enlarged and pulled slightly to the east. Similar modifications of the underlying maps have been made for Brazil, see Symanzik et al. (2014), Figure 1, and China, see Symanzik et al. (2016), Figure 1.
- (ii) Converting a continuous variable into a variable with a few ordered values for the colors that are used in a choropleth map results in an immediate loss of information. — In LMPlots, such transformations are not required. Instead, the exact numerical values often are being shown via dot plots in one or more statistical columns in LMPlots.
- (iii) It is difficult to show more than one variable in a choropleth map. — This can be addressed in LMPlots by using multiple statistical columns or different plot types in a statistical column, e.g., by combining dots with a confidence bound or by displaying a boxplot or a time series plot for each spatial location in the statistical columns.

These features of LMPlots immediately can be carried over to linked micromap plots for point locations. There is no loss of information as the exact values of the variable(s) can be plotted in the statistical columns. Also, multiple statistical columns can be shown to display more than just one variable. And, similar to point (i) above, the point locations that represent the spatial locations of interest can be enlarged to circles or squares that can be colored in the typical way as in LMPlots for areal data. Ultimately, this enlargement of the point locations may need even less space on a map than the space that is needed for ray-glyph maps (Carr et al., 1992; Wickham et al., 2012).

The initial development of linked micromap plots for point locations was initiated independently by two groups of researchers and will be described in Sections 2.1 and 2.2.

2.1 Linked Micromap Plots for Positions on a Baseball Field

In 2010, Daniel B. Carr and Linda W. Pickle published a linked micromap plot based on the positions on a baseball field for major league baseball players during the 2007 season, see Carr and Pickle (2010), Figure 1.5. The point locations are the locations on a baseball

Figure 2: Early variants of Figure 1.5 in Carr and Pickle (2010). (a) shows a variant of the baseball field without the two white foul lines that can be seen in all other variants. (c) and (e) add the foul lines, but differ as (c) only shows the active five positions in each micromap whereas (e) also shows the inactive five positions in each micromap. (b), (d), and (f) also add the foul lines and show the inactive five positions in each micromap and further enlarge the field by cutting off some of the corners. Moreover, three different variants of colors for the positions have been used: (b) uses colors in spectral order, (d) uses colors in default order, and (f) uses a variant of the colors in spectral order that are easier to spot on the background. Ultimately, the published Figure 1.5 in Carr and Pickle (2010) made use of a baseball field similar to the one in (c) and only showed the active five positions in each micromap and combined this with the colors and statistical columns from (b) and made some further changes to the labels and background color. In all parts of this figure, the following abbreviations have been used to label the ten positions: P = pitcher, C = catcher, SS = shortstop, CF = center fielder, 2B = second baseman, 3B = third baseman, LF = left fielder, DH = designated hitter, RF = right fielder, and 1B = first baseman. (Figure parts (a)–(f) courtesy of Daniel B. Carr and Linda W. Pickle.)

field where the various players typically stand. Prior to the release of that figure in 2010, Daniel B. Carr and Linda W. Pickle extensively experimented with the layout, colors and other features for this variant of a linked micromap plot for point locations. Some of these efforts can be seen in Figure 2. Three statistics are shown in this figure: The “Slugging %” measures the batting productivity of a hitter; the “Batting Average” is a calculation to determine a player’s success rate in getting a hit; and the “Total Chances/Game” is the number of opportunities to field the ball defensively and is related to the error rate, or conversely the success rate, of any fielder. Interestingly, all variants shown in this figure reveal a strong spatial pattern that is related to the slugging percentage: The five most central positions on the baseball field have the lowest slugging percentage.

2.2 Linked Micromap Plots for Climate Stations

At about the same time when Daniel B. Carr and Linda W. Pickle developed their version of a linked micromap plot for the positions on a baseball field, researchers at Utah State University, most notably Robert R. Gillies and Jürgen Symanzik, were interested in extending the previously developed experimental linked micromap web page at the Utah Climate Center for the display of climate data, in particular for time series data from climate stations from across the United States. Several graduate students contributed to these efforts, most notable Anuj Thapliyal who extended the original UCC–USU micromap web page to include time series plots for climate stations (Thapliyal, 2009) and Pradeep Kumar Yarra who did some major refactoring (i.e., restructuring the existing source code without changing its visible external behavior) of the web–based software (Yarra, 2010). This refactoring process eliminated unused components from the original NCI web application and internally modified the Java code to better match its use of the West Nile Virus data and climate data.

Some examples of the linked micromap plots for point locations for climate stations across the United States can be found in Figures 3 and 4. While climate stations in Figure 3 (a) and (b) are naturally spaced out fairly well and no overplotting of the stations occurs in the micromaps, several of the climate stations in Figures 3 (c) and (d) are located close to each other, resulting in the overplotting of those stations in the micromaps. No attempt was made in the Java code to resolve the overplotting or partial overplotting of stations during the lifespan of the UCC–USU micromap web page.

3. Construction Steps for Linked Micromaps Plots for Point Locations in R

In this section, we outline necessary steps for constructing linked micromaps plots for point locations from scratch, rather than using preselected data and predefined steps as in a web–based tool as discussed in Section 2.2. Ideally, we want to avoid that the areas (circles or squares) that are created around the point locations overlap and we possibly have to shift some (or all) of them to avoid or at least minimize overplotting. Eventually, we have to consider three main scenarios for the initial point locations. Those are:

- (i) All point locations are spread out fairly well so that there is no overplotting of the points in a LMPlot and therefore no need to shift any of the point locations. This scenario will be discussed in Section 3.1.
- (ii) Some of the point locations are located too close to each other and will result in considerable overplotting in a LMPlot. Therefore, it may be necessary to shift some of the point locations. This shift can be done using some available geographic information in the spatial data set, e.g., single cities in a geographic subunit can be shifted to

Figure 3: Reproduction of Figures 1, 4, 14, and 17 from Thapliyal (2009), showing screenshots of the UCC–USU micromap web page with time series plots of climate stations in (a) San Juan County, Utah, (b) San Diego County, California, (c) Denali County, Alaska, and (d) Kodiak Island County, Alaska. The implementation at the UCC–USU web page used a principle similar to what can be seen in Figure 2 (b), (d), (e), and (f) and marked all locations of the climate stations in the selected county in each of the micromaps. In (b), (c), and (d), climate stations with missing values for the month on display are sorted at the bottom of graph, but still are shown on the micromaps. (Figure parts (a)–(d) courtesy of Anuj Thapliyal.)

the centroid location of their surrounding county. This scenario will be discussed in Section 3.2.

- (iii) Similar to the previous scenario, some of the point locations are located too close to each other and will result in considerable overplotting in a LMPlot. Again, it seems to be necessary to shift some of the point locations. However, in this scenario, there exists no additional geographic information in the spatial data set about where the points can be shifted. Rather, a generic repelling approach is necessary. This scenario will be discussed in Section 3.3.

We will next outline nine steps that need to be followed when constructing linked micromap plots for point locations in R, a free software environment for statistical computing and graphics (R Core Team, 2025). Our description is primarily suited for the *micromap* R package (Payton et al., 2015; Payton and Olsen, 2024) and its underlying data structures. When working with the other main R package for linked micromap plots in R, namely the *micromapST* R package (Pickle et al., 2015; Pearson Jr. and Carr, 2025), or with linked mi-

Figure 4: Reproduction of Figures 5 and 6 from Yarra (2010), showing screenshots of the UCC–USU micromap web page after the refactoring process with time series plots of climate stations in Box Elder County, Utah, for (a) one statistical column and (b) two statistical columns. (Figure parts (a)–(b) courtesy of Pradeep Kumar Yarra.)

chromap plots created outside of R, these steps have to be slightly adapted to the underlying software. All figures in this section have been created with R version 4.5.1 and the R code and data sets available on August 1, 2025, at <https://github.com/symanzik/MicromapPlotsInR/commits/master/06-pointLocations.Rmd>. As is common for code and data that are accessible on such a repository, changes to the code and data likely are going to happen over time, in particular to keep things working when the global environment (here R) gets upgraded or simply to fix bugs or make other enhancements to the code. Other R packages that are directly used for the manipulation of data, maps, and graphics for the examples presented in this section are the *sf* (Pebesma, 2025), *dplyr* (Wickham et al., 2023), *labeling* (Talbot, 2023), *tigris* (Walker, 2025), and *rnaturalearth* (Massicotte and South, 2025) R packages. The repelling of a set of points is based on R code adapted from the *FField* R package (Kapoustin, 2013) that was removed from the Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN) on June 22, 2022.

The nine steps needed for the construction of linked micromap plots for point locations using the *micromap* R package are as follows:

- 1) Obtain coordinates of the point locations of interest along with the corresponding data to display.
- 2) Obtain geographic data for the underlying base map in the background.
- 3) Create a simple plot of the point locations and partially shift overplotting points.
- 4) Create polygons (circles or squares) around the adjusted point locations.
- 5) Combine the base map and the polygons representing point locations into a single spatial object.
- 6) Convert the object created in the previous step into a spatial data frame object.
- 7) Create a basic draft linked micromap plot.
- 8) Repeat Steps 3 to 7 as needed in case there is still too much overplotting or if the polygons are too small for coloring inside the basic linked micromap plot.

9) Add additional visualization elements to the draft linked micromap plot.

In the next three subsections, we take a closer look at three cases studies. In the first case study in Section 3.1, we look at all nine steps from above in detail. In the following two case studies in Sections 3.2 and 3.3, we only look at some selected steps. In all three case studies, we follow the principle seen in Figure 2 (bdef) in Section 2.1 and throughout all figures in Section 2.2 and always show the inactive point locations in addition to the active ones in each of the micromaps. This typically helps a viewer to conceptualize all of the point locations at the same time to get a better feeling of their relative positions, rather than seeing only a few of the point locations at a time in each of the micromaps.

3.1 Case Study #1: Population of the Ten Biggest Cities in Asia

In the first case study, we are interested in constructing linked micromaps for point locations that show the population data from the ten biggest cities in Asia. In Step 1, we have to obtain coordinates of the point locations of interest along with the corresponding data to display. The data, shown in Figure 5, have been obtained from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_Asian_cities_by_population_within_city_limits in early 2022. Most numbers on this web page have been updated since then. However, an archived version from April 19, 2022, with these population counts can be found at https://web.archive.org/web/20220419001036/https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_Asian_cities_by_population_within_city_limits. The population counts that are used in this section is the city proper population, i.e., the population within the geographical area contained within the city limits. Alternatively, the population in the metropolitan area or the population in the urban area, that typically both are larger than the city proper population, could have been used. Latitude and longitude have also been obtained from the Wikipedia pages for these ten cities in early 2022. While there are often some concerns how reliable data from Wikipedia are, the data seem to be reliable enough for this case study.

```
> head(cities)
# A tibble: 6 × 5
  city      country population    lat long
<chr>    <chr>      <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
1 Shanghai China      24256800 31.2 121.
2 Beijing  China      21516000 39.9 116.
3 Mumbai   India      20667656 19.1  72.9
4 Delhi    India      16787941 28.7  77.2
5 Karachi  Pakistan   14910352 24.9  67.0
6 Istanbul Turkey     14657000 41.1  29
```

Figure 5: A tibble in R that shows the city name, the country, the total population, and the latitude and longitude of the six biggest cities in Asia in decreasing order. Overall, data for the ten biggest cities in Asia in 2022 have been obtained.

In Step 2, we have to obtain geographic data for the underlying base map that gets plotted in the background, here countries ranging from Turkey in the west to Japan in the east, shown in Figure 6(a). The idea is to display the country boundaries in the visible part of the map to make it somewhat easier to show in which country a city is located.

Next, in Step 3, we have to create a simple map-based plot of the point locations and partially shift overplotting points if necessary. Here, a simple scatterplot of longitude and latitude, shown in Figure 6(b), is sufficient. The point locations, i.e., the Asian cities, are spread out over the scatterplot, i.e., the map area. There is no apparent need to shift any of these points.

Figure 6: (a) A background map with countries from Asia, ranging from Turkey in the west to Japan in the east. Countries from southeast Asia and northern Asia have been omitted as none of the ten biggest cities in Asia are located in any of those countries. (b) Scatterplot of longitude and latitude of the ten biggest Asian cities. They are spread far from each other. Likely, there is no need to shift any of these points. (c) Circles created around the point locations. As there is only some minimal overlap of the circles representing Karachi and Mumbai in India, no further modifications are necessary for the locations and the circles. (d) Plot of the base map from part (a) and the polygons representing the point locations from part (c) after having been combined into a single spatial data frame object.

Figure 7: (a) Basic linked micromap plot of the point locations of the ten biggest cities in Asia. (b) Refined final linked micromap plot of the point locations of the ten biggest cities in Asia.

In Step 4, polygons (here circles) are created around the (adjusted) point locations, shown in Figure 6(c). Eight of the ten circles do not even touch each other. Two of the circles, representing Karachi and Mumbai in India, slightly overlap. Here, it was decided to keep these circles without any further modifications. Alternatively, one could have reduced the radius of all circles to prevent any overplotting or shift the center for these two cities in opposite directions.

In Steps 5 and 6, the base map from Step 2 and the polygons representing the point locations from Step 4 have to be combined into a single spatial object. Internally, this object then needs to be converted into a spatial data frame object and plotted (see Figure 6(d)) for an assessment of its correctness. It appears that the circles cover the correct areas where these ten cities are located in their corresponding countries.

Now, in Step 7, we can create a basic draft linked micromap plot of the point locations of the ten cities, shown in Figure 7(a). Such a draft plot usually gets created to assess the correctness of the data, the spatial locations, and the underlying data structures. Here, everything looks reasonable.

Step 8 is an assessment of whether it is necessary to repeat Steps 3 to 7 as needed.

Here, it does not seem to be necessary to repeat any of the previous steps. The underlying geography looks fine, the point locations only overplot minimally for just two of the ten cities. So, there is no need to go back to an earlier step.

Thus, in the final Step 9, additional visualization elements can be added to the draft linked micromap plot, e.g., adding meaningful titles and labels, rescaling the statistical panels and the map area, adjusting color to a sequential red color scheme instead of using a rainbow color scheme, and more. The resulting final linked micromap plot for the population of the ten biggest cities in Asia can be seen in Figure 7(b). The cities are sorted in decreasing order of the city proper population. The five biggest cities shown in the top panel and micromap are all located in China, India, and Pakistan. The next five biggest cities are spread out over the entire Asian continent, ranging from Turkey in the west to Japan in the east.

3.2 Case Study #2: Elevation and Population of the 29 County Seats in Utah

In the second case study, we are working with elevation and population data from the county seats of the 29 counties in Utah in the United States. The elevation data have been obtained from <https://onlineutah.us/countyseats.shtml> in early 2022. Similarly, the population data from the 2020 Census for the 29 county seats have also been obtained in early 2022 from <https://opendata.gis.utah.gov/datasets/utah::utah-municipal-boundaries/explore>. Coordinates for the the 29 county seats have been obtained in a Pseudo-Mercator projection (EPSG: 3857) format and represent Easting (X) and Northing (Y) in meters.

We only address two of the nine steps in detail here. In Step 3, we create a simple map-based plot of the point locations and partially shift overplotting points. Many of the 29 county seats are either located in the eastern parts of their corresponding counties to the east of the Great Salt Lake Desert and the Sevier Desert or in somewhat lower elevations towards the western side of the Wasatch Mountain Range. Thus, many of these county seats are aligned in a very narrow band from northern to southern Utah. Therefore, a few of the county seats in northern Utah have been shifted to avoid overplotting, namely the county seats in Weber, Morgan, Davis, Salt Lake, Summit, Wasatch, and Box Elder counties, as shown in Figure 8(a). Here for simplicity, these county seats are shifted to the centroid of their corresponding county, making use of spatial coordinates that naturally come with the underlying geographic information. Alternatively, the county seats could have been shifted to the geographic mid-point of the original location and the centroid location.

We would leave it to the reader to assess whether Step 8 is necessary, i.e., to go back and repeat Steps 3 to 7 here. In fact, it might be worthwhile to shift additional county seats as needed or experiment with the mid-point idea to prevent that some of the county seats get shifted too far away from their original location, which is currently the case for Brigham City in the northwestern corner of Utah.

Ultimately, in the final Step 9, additional visualization elements can be added to the draft linked micromap plot, e.g., adding meaningful titles and labels, rescaling the statistical panels and the map area, adjusting color to a sequential blue color scheme instead of using a rainbow color scheme, and more. The resulting final linked micromap plot for the elevation and population of the 29 county seats in Utah can be seen in Figure 8(b). The county seats are sorted in increasing order of their elevation. Interestingly, the eight county seats with a relatively low elevation that are shown in the top two panels and micromaps all have a relatively large population. The remaining 21 county seats with a higher elevation that are shown in the remaining five panels and micromaps tend to have a relatively small population (based on the 2020 Census data).

Figure 8: (a) County seats in northern Utah where a blue dot represents the original location of the county seat and a red dot represents the shifted location. (b) Refined final linked micromap plot of the point locations of the 29 county seats in Utah.

3.3 Case Study #3: Premier League Football Stadiums in England and Wales in 2018

In the third case study, we are working with stadium capacity and average attendance for the 20 Premier League Football clubs in England and Wales in the 2018–2019 season. This season was chosen as the final full season that took place before the worldwide Covid pandemic in 2020 and 2021. The attendance and capacity data were obtained from https://www.transfermarkt.us/premier-league/besucherzahlen/wettbewerb/GB1/saison_id/2018 in late 2021. The spatial coordinates (in latitude and longitude) for the 20 stadiums of interest were also obtained in late 2021 from <https://www.doogal.co.uk/FootballStadiums.php>. Similar to Case Study #2 from Section 3.2, we once again only address two of the nine steps in detail here.

In Step 3, we create a simple map-based plot of the point locations, shown in Figure 9(a)[left]. There are numerous points that are overplotting as there are several stadium locations in the same city, notably in London, Liverpool, and Manchester. These point locations have to be repelled to avoid overplotting in the linked micromap plot. In contrast to Case Study #2 from Section 3.2, there are no suitable alternative locations for these points immediately available. Rather, it is necessary to use an algorithmic approach to repel points that are initially located too close to each other. The final result is shown in Figure 9(a)[right].

While no details are shown, Step 8 is necessary here to fine-tune the repelling of the point locations. While there are seven stadiums and teams in or around London in the southeast of England that clearly need to be repelled, this repelling should not push any of these locations too close to any other nearby point location, in particular not too close to the AMEX Stadium from Brighton & Hove Albion that is located to the south of London in Brighton and Hove, East Sussex, England. We stopped with the repelling result that is shown in Figure 9(a)[right]. Any additional attempts to further repel the point locations automatically resulted in a layout where some of the London locations and the Brighton & Hove location became mixed up. Readers who think that some of the repelled point locations that are being used here are still too close to each other should manually shift a selected small number of the point locations to a slightly different location.

As in the previous two case studies, in the final Step 9, additional visualization elements can be added to the draft linked micromap plot. The resulting final linked micromap plot for the stadium capacity and average attendance of the 20 Premier League Football clubs in England and Wales in the 2018/2019 season can be seen in Figure 9(b). The stadiums/teams are sorted in decreasing order of their stadium capacity. There is a very strong positive association between stadium capacity and average attendance as the almost perfectly parallel dots in the two statistical panels suggest. However, the two statistical panels also reveal two notable exceptions: Tottenham Hotspur had the second highest stadium capacity in that season, but a considerably lower attendance. In contrast, Fulham FC with the second lowest stadium capacity had an average attendance that considerably exceeded its official stadium capacity. This may be due to stadium renovations and whether the stadium capacity was reported before or after the start of the renovations.

4. Summary, Conclusion, and Future Work

This article focused on linked micromap plots for point locations from a historical and conceptual perspective. Similar to regular linked micromap plots for areal data, linked micromap plots for point locations offer an alternative way to display multiple statistical variables in a map-based context. In case the point locations are already placed suitably far away from each other, they can be immediately enlarged to circular or quadratic areas

Figure 9: (a) [Left] Original point locations of the 20 Premier League Football clubs in England and Wales in the 2018/2019 season. There is some considerable overlap of stadiums and teams in the southeast of England with seven teams in and around London, with two teams in Manchester in the central part of England, and with another two teams in Liverpool in the central western part of England. [Right] After using an automatic repelling approach for the original point locations, the resulting repelled point locations are separated quite well. Note that point locations with no immediate neighbors did not get moved at all. (b) Refined final linked micromap plot of the point locations of the 20 Premier League Football clubs in England and Wales in the 2018/2019 season.

around the original point locations and then be used directly in linked micromap plots. Otherwise, some (or all) of the point locations may have to be shifted. This can be based on centroids for an enclosing spatial unit or via some repelling algorithm, possibly with some manual fine-tuning at the end. Then the shifted point locations can be used in linked micromap plots.

This article is complemented by a related forthcoming book chapter by Martin Holdrege and Jürgen Symanzik, called “*Linked Micromap Plots for Point Locations*”, that focuses on the programming aspects of such linked micromap plots. The book with the tentative title “*Micromap Plots in R: A Step-By-Step Approach to Visualize Spatial Data via Linked Micromaps, Conditioned Micromaps, and Comparative Micromaps in R*” is edited by Jürgen Symanzik and contains chapters on the *micromap* and *micromapST* R packages, shapefile modifications for use in micromap applications, additional glyph types and extensions for micromaps, linked micromap plots for point locations (the basis of this article), web applications, conditioned choropleth maps (CCmaps), comparative micromaps, non-traditional micromaps, and applications in the environmental and medical fields. The book will be tentatively released in late 2026 through Taylor & Francis / CRC Press. All R code and data sets in support of the book (including those used for this article) can be found at <https://github.com/symanzik/MicromapPlotsInR>.

A few programmatic additions for linked micromap plots for point locations would be desirable, in particular the capability to display time series plots in the statistical panels for linked micromap plots for point locations, similar to the examples from the UCC-USU micromap web page that were discussed in Section 2.2. Also, it seems to be worthwhile to experiment with modified shapefiles for point locations for use in the *micromapST* R package. Ultimately, it seems to be necessary to standardize and extend some of the functionality described in this article for future use in web-based linked micromaps for point locations.

References

- Carr, D. B., Olsen, A. R., Courbois, J.-Y. P., Pierson, S. M., and Carr, D. A. (1998a). Linked Micromap Plots: Named and Described. *Statistical Computing and Statistical Graphics Newsletter*, 9(1):24–32.
- Carr, D. B., Olsen, A. R., Pierson, S. M., and Courbois, J.-Y. P. (1998b). Boxplot Variations in a Spatial Context: An Omernik Ecoregion and Weather Example. *Statistical Computing and Statistical Graphics Newsletter*, 9(2):4–13.
- Carr, D. B., Olsen, A. R., and White, D. (1992). Hexagon Mosaic Maps for Display of Univariate and Bivariate Geographical Data. *Cartography and Geographic Information Systems*, 19(4):228–236, 271. <https://doi.org/10.1559/152304092783721231>.
- Carr, D. B. and Pickle, L. W. (2010). *Visualizing Data Patterns with Micromaps*. Chapman & Hall / CRC, Boca Raton, FL.
- Carr, D. B. and Pierson, S. M. (1996). Emphasizing Statistical Summaries and Showing Spatial Context with Micromaps. *Statistical Computing and Statistical Graphics Newsletter*, 7(3):16–23.
- Chapala, G. K. (2005). Development of Rich Features for Web-Based Interactive Micromaps. MS Report, Utah State University, Department of Computer Science, Logan, UT.
- Chen, J. X., Carr, D. B., Wechsler, H., and Pan, Z. (2006). Interactive Visualization of Multivariate Statistical Data. *The International Journal of Virtual Reality*, 5(3):67–73. <https://doi.org/10.20870/IJVR.2006.5.3.2701>.
- Kapoustin, G. (2013). *FField: Force Field Simulation for a Set of Points*. R package version 0.1.0 (<http://CRAN.R-project.org/package=FField>).
- Massicotte, P. and South, A. (2025). *rnaturalearth: World Map Data from Natural Earth*. R package version 1.1.0 (<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=rnaturalearth>).
- Olsen, A. R., Carr, D. B., Courbois, J.-Y. P., and Pierson, S. M. (1996). Presentation of Data in

- Linked Attribute and Geographic Space. In *1996 Abstracts, Joint Statistical Meetings, Chicago, Illinois*, page 271. American Statistical Association, Alexandria, VA.
- Payton, Q. C., McManus, M. G., Weber, M. H., Olsen, A. R., and Kincaid, T. M. (2015). *micromap: A Package for Linked Micromaps*. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 63(2):1–16. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v063.i02>.
- Payton, Q. C. and Olsen, A. R. (2024). *micromap: Linked Micromap Plots*. R package version 1.9.10 (<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=micromap>).
- Pearson Jr., J. B. and Carr, D. B. (2025). *micromapST: Linked Micromap Plots for U. S. and Other Geographic Areas*. R package version 3.1.1 (<http://CRAN.R-project.org/package=micromapST>).
- Pebesma, E. (2025). *sf: Simple Features for R*. R package version 1.0–21 (<http://CRAN.R-project.org/package=sf>).
- Pickle, L. W., Pearson Jr., J. B., and Carr, D. B. (2015). *micromapST: Exploring and Communicating Geospatial Patterns in US State Data*. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 63(3):1–25. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v063.i03>.
- R Core Team (2025). *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <http://www.R-project.org/>.
- Symanzik, J., Bao, S., Dai, X., Shui, M., and She, B. (2016). Recent Advancements in Geovisualization, with a Case Study on Chinese Religions. In Jin, Z., Liu, M., and Luo, X., editors, *New Developments in Statistical Modeling, Inference and Application: Selected Papers from the 2014 ICASA/KISS Joint Applied Statistics Symposium in Portland, OR*, pages 151–166. Springer, Cham, Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-42571-9_8.
- Symanzik, J. and Carr, D. B. (2008). Interactive Linked Micromap Plots for the Display of Geographically Referenced Statistical Data. In Chen, C., Härdle, W., and Unwin, A., editors, *Handbook of Data Visualization*, pages 267–294 & 2 Color Plates. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Symanzik, J. and Carr, D. B. (2013). Linked Micromap Plots in R. In Cho, S.-H., editor, *Proceedings of IASC–Satellite Conference for the 59th ISI WSC & The 8th Conference of IASC–ARS*, pages 213–218. Asian Regional Section of the IASC.
- Symanzik, J., Carr, D. B., McManus, M. G., and Weber, M. H. (2017). Micromaps. In *Wiley StatsRef: Statistics Reference Online*. Wiley Online Library. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118445112.stat07938>.
- Symanzik, J., Dai, X., Weber, M. H., Payton, Q., and McManus, M. G. (2014). Linked Micromap Plots for South America — General Design Considerations and Specific Adjustments. *Revista Colombiana de Estadística*, 37(2):451–469. <https://doi.org/10.15446/rce.v37n2spe.47949>.
- Symanzik, J., Gebreab, S., Gillies, R., and Wilson, J. (2003). Visualizing the Spread of West Nile Virus. In *2003 JSM Proceedings*. American Statistical Association, Alexandria, VA. (CD).
- Talbot, J. (2023). *labeling: Axis Labeling*. R package version 0.4.3 (<http://CRAN.R-project.org/package=labeling>).
- Thapliyal, A. (2009). Enhancement of Web–based Interactive Micromaps. MS Report, Utah State University, Department of Computer Science, Logan, UT.
- Walker, K. (2025). *tigris: Load Census TIGER/Line Shapefiles*. R package version 2.2.1, (<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=tigris>).
- Wang, X., Chen, J. X., Carr, D. B., Bell, B. S., and Pickle, L. W. (2002). Geographic Statistics Visualization: Web–based Linked Micromap Plots. *Computing in Science & Engineering*, 4(3):90–94. <https://doi.org/10.1109/5992.998645>.
- Wickham, H., François, R., Henry, L., Müller, K., and Vaughan, D. (2023). *dplyr: A Grammar of Data Manipulation*. R package version 1.1.4 (<http://CRAN.R-project.org/package=dplyr>).
- Wickham, H., Hofmann, H., Wickham, C., and Cook, D. (2012). Glyph–maps for Visually Exploring Temporal Patterns in Climate Data and Models. *Environmetrics*, 23(5):382–393. <https://doi.org/10.1002/env.2152>.
- Yarra, P. K. (2010). Refactoring Micromaps. MS Report, Utah State University, Department of Computer Science, Logan, UT.